

THE POSITIVE IMPACT OF GYMNASTICS WITH PILATES ON THE HEALTH AND WELL-BEING OF YOUNG WOMEN

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Abstract. This paper presents a new exercise program for young women, which includes Pilates and yoga. The main aim of the program is to help the women in the training group to become fit and healthy after a long COVID break. The positive impact of this program is approved by the results of our questionnaire research of the participants. All recovered almost entirely from covid. Women changed their style, became more sportive and joyful. The program is good for recovery from covid, at the same time it helps all women to improve quality of everyday life by feeling healthy, active and happy. We may recommend this program for all young active women, who have not too much free time for sport.

Keywords: Pilates, Covid 19, breathing exercises, rhythmic gymnastics, yoga.

Introduction. Pilates comes from the name of Joseph Pilates, who developed this technique in the middle of the 20th century. It uses a series of stretching, strengthening and breathing exercises that activate your muscles and promote cellular health. According to the latest scientific data Pilates appeared to be effective during the Covid 19 pandemic [1-3].

Over the years, Pilates has become a popular form of exercise. We can do Pilates using just a mat, or we can add tools and equipment like a Pilates reformer (Fig. 1). Either option can give us amazing results.

Fig. 1. The use of Pilates reformer and Pilates magic ring.

Of course, Pilates and yoga are similar at first glance. Both are popular forms of exercise that use stretching and breathing techniques to improve the person's overall health. But they also have some important differences.

Pilates is a low-impact exercise that focuses on performing small movements, relying on the person's back and muscles for stabilization. The main physical benefits of Pilates are improving core strength and achieving better posture.

Yoga focuses on concentration and deep breathing as the person goes through a series of poses. It is often used to deepen meditation practice, increase flexibility and improve balance.

This paper presents the results from a new fitness program providing Pilates for women, which started in October 2022.

Objectives. The main goal of our program was to help the women in the training group to become fit and healthy after a long COVID break. The program was supposed to help those women, who had the COVID virus to rehabilitate completely using breathing exercises of this unique program, as there is significant evidence demonstrating that the COVID virus weakens the respiratory system, which can considerably deteriorate the quality of everyday life.

Materials and Methods. For this program, 10 young women (average age 38-40 years old) have been selected. It was extremely interesting for us to start this new program with ladies, who do not practice any other sport except healthy daily walking. Their good basic level of fitness meant one-hour training sessions could be held twice a week. Most of the participants work full-time office hours, have young children, as all are parents of children in a primary school, where gymnastics was taught. They had limited time for any other sport during their working week due to the many obligations and responsibilities that active young women usually have.

At the start, we had to evaluate the physical condition of each lady in the group to understand personal goals and how we could reach them by following a range of activities such as gymnastics with elements of Pilates, rhythmic gymnastics, yoga for flexibility and dancing for joy. The activity takes place in a gymnastics hall in a school and the only equipment required is individual mats. Another goal was also to choose a program that is as COVID-safe as possible, as there were still many cases around despite of the fact that lockdown was over.

Fig. 2. Pilates class.

We found the space good enough, to keep distance for each participant to enjoy personal healthy space. Individual mats assured hygiene demands, also the space had good ventilation conditions to have fresh clean air for better quality of breathing exercises. We limit the number of participants in a group to ten which created a fun-filled positive joyful group atmosphere and, at the same time, ensured we could assist each lady to do new movements the most efficient and safe way. Fortunately, this gymnastics hall had a little stage, which was very helpful for participants. It helped participants to see the coach to allow new movements to be easily taught.

To create this amazing first level program, we researched and followed different existing ways of teaching Pilates in different countries. For example, Germany, France, United States, Russia and Great Britain. There are basic classical movements of Pilates that are used in all programs worldwide, though taking into consideration the group's special needs and goals, the program may vary considerably from a very basic level to more advanced.

At the beginning of the course, during the first month, we started with the basic level simple mild Pilates classical movements on mats with a special accent on breathing technics and controlling big and small muscles. It was especially important, to increase the difficulty of movements gradually to keep a positive impact without hurting any muscles, as most of the women were not fit. At the same time learning breathing technics helped those women, who were recovering after covid, to be at the same level as other women in the group.

We used to show two types of movement implementation with different levels of difficulty, this way women could choose the best suitable for their level way, being in the same group. It was important to understand, that in Pilates we focus on our own body feeling well from the inside and not to compare with others. This helped women to feel comfortable.

Important details are the following:

1. Clothes made of soft, comfortable and breathable textures are better;
2. Special Pilates mats help to feel more comfortable, healthy hygiene and allowed assistance in-person while others continued implementation;
3. Music background is essential for the best positive impact, Music to be chosen carefully chosen in advance, at the beginning more dynamic and relaxing calming in the main part;
4. Warmup is extremely important to wake up muscles and avoid any injuries, also to learn doing any sport wisely in the future;
5. Explain and show slowly each new movement to assure good understanding from inside;
6. Friendly positive atmosphere great for well-being feeling Happy and inspired;
7. Little delightful ending of the program with fun cognitive movements, yoga favorites for flexibility or some light dancing with a favorite song to return at home always in high spirits;
8. First we added Pilates small balls and exercise band and after winter break for holidays we added also Pilates magic rings. We have noticed that it motivated women to continue the course introducing new apparatus gradually learning something new was always exciting.

Research results and discussion. After completing the 4-month exercise program all participants were asked to estimate the functioning of their organ systems (respiratory, cardiovascular, digestive, nervous and muscular/skeletal) before starting the program and after the program completion using a five grade scale (1 – bad, 2 – not so bad, 3 – normal, 4 – good, 5 – very good). The results of the self-assessment are shown in tables 1, 2.

From the tables, we can see that the condition of almost all participants has improved (the post-Covid participant's data are shown in grey color). We have calculated mean values for all organ systems.

We can see, that all mean values improved significantly after the training: the improvements in almost all organ systems turned out to be more significant in the case of the post-Covid participants, the training appeared to be more effective for respiratory, nervous and muscular/skeletal systems and less effective for cardiovascular and digestive systems. The last fact may be explained by taking into account the age of the participants, who were 38-40 years old young women and had good cardiovascular and digestive systems, while their other organ systems were weakened after the pandemic.

Table 1. Self-estimation of the functioning of participants' organ systems before the training.

Organ System	Participant Nº and self-evaluations										Mean values		
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	After Covid	No Covid	All
1 Respiratory	2	2	4	3	3	4	3	2	2	2	2.25	2.89	2.70
2 Cardiovascular	3	2	3	4	5	5	4	2	3	4	3.00	3.71	3.50
3 Digestive	2	2	2	3	3	4	4	3	2	3	2.75	2.82	2.80
4 Nervous	3	3	3	3	3	4	3	3	3	2	2.75	3.11	3.00
5 Muscular/Skeletal	2	2	2	2	3	4	3	2	2	2	2.00	2.57	2.40

Table 2. Self-estimation of the functioning of participants' organ systems after the training.

Organ System	Participant Nº and self-evaluations										Mean values		
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	After Covid	No Covid	All
1 Respiratory	5	4	5	5	4	5	5	4	4	4	4.25	4.61	4.50
2 Cardiovascular	5	4	5	5	5	5	5	4	5	5	4.50	4.93	4.80
3 Digestive	4	5	4	4	5	5	5	5	4	4	4.50	4.50	4.50
4 Nervous	5	4	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	4.75	4.96	4.90
5 Muscular/Skeletal	4	4	4	5	5	5	5	4	4	4	4.25	4.46	4.40

Conclusion. This way our program remained sustainable healthy and happy for all. Women changed their style, and became more sportive and joyful. All recovered almost entirely from covid. The positive impact of this program also approves our questionnaire research of the participants. Here you may see the answers and it is obvious that all the indicators were more or less improved after the course.

The program is good for recovery from covid, at the same time it helps all women to improve quality of everyday life by feeling healthy, active and happy. Be well and lead well their beloved families and kids in their everyday family life. We may recommend this program for all young active women, who have not too much free time for sport.

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